

Polycyclic Systems. Part XIII¹. A New Synthesis of 1,2-Benzanthracene

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A new flexible route to 1,2-benzanthracene is described starting from 2- β -naphthylethyl bromide and ethyl β -oxopimelate through the successive steps of alkylation, cyclodehydration, Dieckmann condensation, and aromatisation of appropriate derivatives.

Cyclodehydration of substituted aralkyl- β -oxopimelate (I; R = Ar.CH₂CH₂-) and subsequent elaboration of the products have been extensively used in our laboratory for the synthesis of a number of useful polycyclic systems²⁻⁴. No β -substituted naphthalene derivative (*e.g.*, II) has however been employed in these reactions. These compounds are capable of undergoing both linear and angular cyclisation and the purpose of the present work is to determine which would be the preferred ring-closure and to what extent the products could be utilised for the synthesis of other polycyclic hydrocarbons.

Accordingly, 2- β -naphthylethyl bromide was condensed with ethyl β -oxopimelate⁵ (I; R = H) under the usual condition and the resultant substituted β -oxo-ester (II) cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid at -10° . The product on hydrolysis furnished a crystalline dicarboxylic acid (III) the yield of which was found to be variable (30–60%) and extremely sensitive to the temperature and amount of sulphuric acid used. The structure of acid (III)

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followed from its subsequent conversion into 1,2-benzanthracene (V) through the undermentioned sequence of reaction.

The methyl ester (as III) was submitted to Dieckmann cyclisation and the resulting β -oxo-ester (IV; R=CO₂Me, R'=H) hydrolysed to the tetracyclic ketone (IV; R=R'=H), m.p. 135°. This was smoothly converted into (a) 1,2-benzanthracene (V; R = H) and (b) its 4-methyl derivative (V; R = Me) by (a) reduction with lithium aluminium hydride, and (b) addition of methylmagnesium iodide followed by dehydration and dehydrogenation with 30% palladium-charcoal. The hydrocarbons were characterised by their m.p.s, formation of picrates and trinitrofluorenone complex.

The linear cyclisation involving the less reactive β -position of naphthalene is evidently due to a repulsive interaction between R and R' in (vii) in the forming hydrophenanthrene ring if angular ring-closure is to take place and is well-documented by numerous examples⁶⁻⁸. From a perusal of different ring-closures of this type, a general rule may be formulated as follows: If in a molecule (VII) both R and R' are hydrogen (R' may even be -OH), angular cyclisation would take place; on the other hand if one or both of them are alkyls, linear cyclisation would prevail. Thus the aldehyde (VII; R = R' = R'' = R''' = H)⁷, the acids (VII; R = R'' = R''' = H, R' = OH)⁹ and (VII; R = H, R' = OH, R'' and R''' forming part of cyclohexanone ring)³ all undergo angular cyclisation, while the ketone (VII; R = R'' = R''' = H; R' = Et)⁶ and the acid¹⁰ (VII; R = Me, R' = OH, R'' = R''' = H) form the anthracene derivative. The rule is applicable apparently to a six-membered ring-closure. In case of a five-membered ring-closure, the 4.5-interaction is appreciably diminished and angular cyclisation takes place even though one of the two groups, R and R' is alkyl. Thus 5- β -naphthylpentan-3-one (VIII) cyclises to the benzindene-derivative (IX)⁷.

The tetracyclic β -oxo-ester (IV; R = H, R' = CO₂Me) could in principle be further annealed by Mannich-Robinson procedure¹¹ and the method be extended to a synthesis of benzchrysene system (VI) (cf. synthesis of picene¹²). The present procedure thus not only provides a useful synthetic route to benzanthracene derivatives but also to still higher polycyclic hydrocarbons.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl β -Oxopimelate (I; R = H): This was prepared in quantity following essentially the method of Guha and Nasipuri⁵.

2- β -Naphthylethyl Bromide: β -Naphthylacetic acid¹³ was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride in ethereal solution in the usual way. β -2-Naphthylethyl alcohol. b.p.

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160°/4 mm. was obtained in colourless crystals, m.p. 67°. A mixture of this alcohol (26 g.), dry carbon tetrachloride (25 ml.) and phosphorus tribromide (20 g.) was heated on the water bath for 1 hour. After working up in the usual way, 2- β -naphthylethyl bromide (28 g.) was obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 140°/15 mm. which solidified on cooling, m.p. 59° (Found : C, 61.1; H, 4.4%. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₁Br : C, 61.3; H, 4.6%) (lit.¹⁴ m.p. 59°).

Ethyl α -2-(β -Naphthylethyl)- β -oxopimelate (II) : To a solution of potassium *tert.* butylate prepared from potassium (1.8 g.) and *tert.* butanol (30 ml.), ethyl β -oxopimelate (10 g.) was added, followed by 2- β -naphthylethyl bromide (9 g.) and the whole refluxed on the water bath for 8 hr. under N₂. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, and the organic matter extracted with ether. The residue (10 g.) after evaporation of solvent was directly cyclised.

2-Carboxy-3,4-dihydro-1-anthracyl- γ -butyric Acid (III) : In a typical experiment, the foregoing crude β -oxo-ester (II) (6.0 g.) was added dropwise into concentrated sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.84) (18 ml.) cooled in a freezing mixture. The red solution was stirred for 30 min. and then decomposed with ice-water. The organic matter collected by ether extraction was hydrolysed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (10%) and the *dicarboxylic acid* (III) obtained as solid. This was filtered and dried to afford the crude acid, m.p. 140–145° (3.2 g.; 60%). An analytical sample, prepared by crystallization from benzene-petroleum had m.p. 150–155°. (Found : C, 73.2; H, 5.6%; C₁₉H₁₈O₄ requires C, 73.5; H, 5.8%). In subsequent experiments, the crude acid was directly esterified by heating with a mixture of 6% methanolic sulphuric acid. The *ester* was obtained as a gum, b.p. 240–245°/4 mm. (Found : C, 74.2; H, 6.2%; C₂₁H₂₂O₄ requires C, 74.5; H, 6.5%).

The Tetracyclic Ketone (IV; R = R' = H) : The foregoing ester (5.5 g.) was heated with pulverised sodium (0.5 g.) in a suspension of benzene (20 ml.) on the water-bath for 4 hr. The viscous solution was decomposed with acid and the resulting β -oxo-ester (5.4 g.) (IV; R = H; R' = COOMe) worked up in the usual way. This was hydrolysed by a refluxing mixture of glacial acetic acid (25 ml.), hydrochloric acid (12.5 ml.), and water (2 ml.) for 4 hr. The solution was diluted with water, the organic matter extracted with ether, the ethereal layer thoroughly washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent evaporated. The residual gum was sublimed at 215–220°/0.5 mm. and afforded white granules (1.8 g.), m.p. 135° from benzene-petroleum ether (Found : C, 86.8; H, 6.2%. C₁₈H₁₆O requires C, 87.1; H, 6.4%). It formed a *dinitrophenylhydrazone* which crystallised from methanol in red amorphous powder, m.p. 203–205° (Found : C, 67.1; H, 4.5; N, 13.0%. C₂₄H₂₀O₄N₄ requires C, 67.3; H, 5.6; N, 13.1%).

1,2-Benzanthracene (V, R = H) : The above ketone (0.5 g.) was reduced with an excess of ethereal solution of lithium aluminium hydride and the resulting alcohol, obtained as a gum (0.5 g.) was intimately mixed with 30% palladium-charcoal¹⁵ (0.2 g.) and heated at 300–340° for 1 hr. The product was extracted with hot benzene, the benzene solution eluted through alumina (10 g.), and finally evaporated to furnish 1,2-benzanthracene as crystalline solid (0.2 g.). This was crystallised several times from benzene-petroleum ether

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in white flakes, m.p. 158–159° (Found : C, 94.5; H, 5.1. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{12}$: C, 94.7; H, 5.2%). The picrate was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in red needles, m.p. 144–145° (Found : C, 63.1; H, 3.4; N, 9.2. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{15}O_7N_3$: C, 63.0; H, 3.3; N, 9.2%). The reported¹⁶ m.p.s. of the hydrocarbon and the picrate are 158°, 133° respectively. The *trinitrofluorenone* complex¹⁷ formed readily and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in orange powder, m.p. 220–221° (Found : C, 68.4; H, 3.0; N, 7.65. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{17}O_7N_3$: C, 68.5; H, 3.1; N, 7.7%); lit¹⁷ m.p. 223–224° (from ethanol).

4-Methyl-1',2'-benzanthracene (V; R = Me) : In another experiment, the tetracyclic ketone (IV; R = R' = H) (0.5 g.) was heated with an excess of methylmagnesium iodide in ether. The resulting alcohol was likewise dehydrogenated with 30% palladium-charcoal and the hydrocarbon recovered as before. 4-Methylbenzanthracene (V; R = Me) (0.25 g.) was obtained in white flakes from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 196° (Found : C, 94.1; H, 5.7. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{14}$: C, 94.2; H, 5.8%). It formed a red picrate (from benzene), m.p. 140° (Found : C, 63.6; H, 3.5. Calc. for $C_{25}H_{17}O_7N_3$: C, 63.7; H, 3.6%). Reported¹⁸ m.p.s. are 194–5°, 139–40° respectively. The *trinitrofluorenone complex* was obtained from acetic acid as orange powder, m.p. 220° (Found : N, 7.65. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{19}O_7N_3$: N, 7.5%).

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